

THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF THERMOFORMED DISCONTINUOUS ALIGNED FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Specimens made of Discontinuous Aligned Fiber (DAF) composite material were elongated to different states of deformation by thermoforming. Tension-tension-fatigue tests were performed using unidirectional and bidirectional specimens cut out of the thermoformed parts. These tests resulted in Wöhler-curves which display an increase in dynamic properties with an increase in elongation not exceeding 9%. In addition, the static strength values also increased with the elongation of the specimens up until 3% due to alignment processes and built-in internal stresses. A decline in the static and dynamic properties for deformations greater than 9% were due to consolidation problems. In order to characterize the internal structure of the samples, they were nondestructively inspected by ultrasonic and thermographic devices.

INTRODUCTION

The growth in the use of plastic composites has resulted in a need for high productivity manufacturing processes [1]. Thermoforming is seen to be the most promising production technique for high-volume processing of advanced continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite parts. It offers several advantages over traditional processing of thermosetting composites into complex geometries such as infinite shelf life of the prepreg and the possibility of in-situ consolidation. However, some important processing issues have to be resolved before this can become a viable economical process [2]. These include fiber placement control, low cycle times for molding and wrinkle-free complex shape forming. The latter requires time consuming interply and intraply slip mechanisms to occur (Fig. 1).

In order to avoid buckling problems while having acceptable processing times, the Discontinuous Aligned Fiber (DAF) composite material providing a "drawable" feature was developed to overcome the thermoforming limitations encountered with continuous fiber systems. DAF consists of aligned carbon fibers with an average length of 50 mm embedded in a PEKK-matrix, with a fiber volume fraction of approximately 58%. Concerns about the strength and stiffness properties of undeformed DAF-material can be neglected due to the length and the nearly perfect alignment of the fibers. Mathematically, maximum fiber reinforcement efficiency is achieved when the fiber length exceeds 50 times the critical fiber length. The critical fiber length of the AS-4 carbon/PEKK composite system can be estimated to be 0.13 mm [3]. Therefore, the ratio of fiber length and critical fiber length is about 380.

Fig. 1: Problems of thermoforming

However, considerations have to be made about the effect of the fiber ends and the distance between them on the dynamic performance of this material system. From injection molded, short fiber composites, it is well known that fiber ends must be considered as potential weak points in a laminate due to small voids and missing interfacial bonding in this area. Furthermore, the movement of tensioned fibers with different length in a viscous matrix can not be expected to happen in a totally homogeneous matter. Both effects may lead to decreases in the static, but especially in the dynamic properties. In order to analyze these effects, the following objectives were defined:

1. Construction of a thermoforming device for the generation of certain states of deformation
2. Determination of an optimal processing window
3. Static and dynamic testing of unidirectional specimens of different deformation states
4. Modelling

MATERIAL AND THERMOFORMING PROCEDURE

The material used in this study was a discontinuous but highly aligned carbon fiber (CF) AS-4/PEKK system described previously. Platens with a thickness of approximately 2 mm and lay-up sequence of $[0^\circ]_{16}$ and $[(90, 0)_7 90]$ were cut into specimens of a width of 27 mm and a length of 400 mm. In order to generate desired states of deformation in the specimens prior to the fatigue tests, they were subjected to a thermoforming procedure. In general, thermoforming of composites involves (a) heating a cold fiber reinforced sheet above melting temperature (T_m) of the semicrystalline or above the glass-transition-temperature (T_g) of the amorphous polymer matrix, (b) forming it into the predetermined shape, and finally (c) rapid cooling of the part. The forming process of the DAF-samples was realized as a particular kind of a stretch-forming process [4, 5]. The stretch-forming was carried out using a setup consisting of a tensile testing machine providing the tensile force F and a laboratory hot press integrated into the testing machine (Fig. 2). Previous experiments had shown that the use of a press tool was necessary in order to apply a sufficiently high pressure (13.6 MPa). This press tool, width 28 mm and length of 160 mm, was placed between the heated plates. Before thermoforming, the heating plates had

to be coated with a thin film of a release agent and covered with a sheet of polyimide foil in order to allow easy demolding. It was aimed to generate elongations of 3%, 6%, 9%, and 12% of the 160 mm specimen length.

Fig 2: Schematic representation of the thermoforming setup

Fig. 3 shows the temperature-pressure course of the deformation process. After preheating up the sample to 390 °C, it was deformed without external pressure. Once the desired elongation (speed of deformation = 0.5 mm/s) was reached, a consolidation pressure of 13.6 MPa was applied and the sample was cooled down. The sample was removed after the temperature dropped below the crystallization temperature of the PEKK-matrix (255 °C).

Fig. 3: Temperature-pressure course of the stretch-forming process

The evaluation of stress-deformation-curves (Fig. 4) indicated thixotropic behavior in terms of a beginning sheat flow. Generally, if any kind of internal bondings in the microstructure of a material has to be dissolved, a higher force has to be provided in the beginning of the forming process. After the destruction of these bonds, the force requirement decreases and converges to an assymtotic limit.

Fig. 4: Stress-deformation-curve during thermoforming of bidirectional DAF

Ultrasonic-C-scans indicated that the consolidation quality of the thermoformed samples was significantly influenced by the deformation state and the pressure applied. Samples with a state of deformation of 12 % exhibited distinct areas of poor consolidation. Microcuts showed a higher void content in these areas than it could be found in microscopic pictures taken from better compacted samples [6]. Poorly consolidated zones were due to a highly localized deformation which caused a slight decrease in thickness of the part. If such a section is thinner than that of its surrounding area, the pressure applied during the post-consolidation process remains low due to the missing contact between matched metal tool and specimen surface. This problem is common in forming high performance thermoplastic composites, and is overcome by using a compliant material such as a high temperature rubber on one of the tool surfaces to obtain uniform consolidation pressure over the entire specimen surface. Such a method for consolidating thermoplastic composites will allow to maintain a uniform fiber to matrix ratio throughout the samples. Unfortunately, the test fixture used to elongate specimens in this study did not allow the use of a compliant tool surface to accommodate specimen thickness uniformities. Therefore, higher post consolidation pressures were applied to the deformed specimens, which essentially squeezed thermoplastic matrix from the unelongated regions to the deformed and simultaneously necked areas.

The question when this local deformation started can be answered by analyzing Fig. 4. As long as the tensile stress remains below a certain value (the "high temperature yield stress"), the deformation occurs uniformly over the entire part of the specimen heated in the press. However, once the tensile stress locally exceeds the yield stress level any further deformation will preferably take place in this section. The reasons for this behavior are:

1. The temperature decreases between the middle of the platens to the side of about 20°C causing a lower viscosity in the middle of it.
2. Many fibers were rigidly clamped in the unmolten material outside the hot press. Thus, the fibers at the pulling side were simply pulled out. The greatest loss of fibers occurred in the middle of the heated part of the sample due to the fiber length distribution.
3. A nonhomogeneous movement of fibers is energetically preferred [7].

TENSILE AND FATIGUE TESTS

The tensile tests on the unidirectional samples were performed according to ASTM 3039 employing a Zwick 1485 universal tensile testing machine. Fig. 5 depicts that the state of pre-deformation has an obvious influence on the tensile strength of uni- bidirectional laminated DAF-samples.

Fig. 5: Tensile strength of thermoformed uni- and bidirectional DAF-samples

The increase in the tensile values for both laminate structures can be explained by three different effects. First, the thermoforming process induces internal stresses in the material as it can be easily seen in Fig. 4 (saturation value of stress). A specimen stretched by 3 % was consolidated while subjected to permanent tensile stress of approximately 100 MPa resulting in a residual compressive stress which has to be overcome during tensile testing. Furthermore, despite the nearly perfect alignment of the discontinuous fibers they are not as well aligned as continuous fibers. Therefore, fiber alignment processes occurred increasing the laminate's tensile strength. The drop in the tensile values for the 12% deformed samples was due to the poor consolidation. Moreover, a decrease in the fiber volume fraction of approximately 3 % was proved by microscopic analysis. However, such little changes in the fiber volume fraction are not significant enough in order to explain this effect.

A Schenck servohydraulic testing machine with a force capacity in the range of 1 to 250 kN was applied for the force controlled fatigue tests. Parallel sided specimens were used for this investigation. They were cut out of the thermoformed samples having a width of 10 mm. The ratio R between minimum and maximum dynamic load was commonly chosen as 0.1. In previous experiments, the optimal cycling frequency in terms of specimen temperature and total cycling time was determined to be 15 Hz. The fatigue tests were permanently monitored by a thermography camera which was connected to a video cassette recorder (VCR). This infrared camera allowed the observation of the damage accumulation occurring in the cycled samples. The results of the fatigue test of unidirectional and bidirectional samples are shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. It has to be noted that the static and dynamic values are referenced in both figures to the maximum static value.

Fig. 6: Wöhler curve of unidirectional DAF-samples with different states of deformation

The dynamic properties increase with an increase in elongation till 9%. However, also the 12%-values are higher than those of 3% or 6% which is due to the additional matrix squeezed into the thinned areas. To research this phenomenon, additional PEKK-foil was compression welded onto some of the DAF-specimens which were then dynamically tested. It turned out that these specially treated samples had a longer life time than non-impregnated ones. The additional matrix acted like a crack stopper for the cracks emerging parallel to the fibers.

Fig. 7: Wöhler curve of bidirectional DAF-samples with different states of deformation

The results for the bidirectional specimens are similar to the outcome of the fatigue tests with the unidirectional samples. However, the increase in life time is less than in case of a unidirectional stacking sequence. The scattering of the values is due to the outer 90°-layers which react very sensitive to surface scratches.

The analysis of the damage accumulation process did not show a significant influence of the fiber ends on the fatigue behavior. In the contrary, permanent thermographic monitoring and ultrasonic inspection of particularly selected samples did not reveal the occurrence of delaminations. Furthermore, both nondestructive methods could not be used to predict final breakage of samples - they broke spontaneously without previous notice. It is obvious that the damage accumulation occurs differently from reinforced thermosets. Additional ultrasonic inspection done on specimens cycled to certain numbers of cycles up to 100 000 cycles at 60% and 70% of the ultimate tensile strength exhibited an increase in the material's damping properties. This effect is caused by local plastic strains in the material lowering the internal bondings and thus the ultrasound conduction. The saturation with transverse cracks was found at a density of 1.9 cracks/mm. These results are in good correspondence to the results of Henaff-Gardin [8].

The damage accumulation can be divided in two parts. Until reaching the characteristic damage state (CDS) level the number of transverse cracks increases. The CDS-level is defined as a certain threshold when no further significant increase in transverse cracks can be observed. During the second step no delamination and longitudinal cracks will be created; however, remaining matrix bridges between transverse cracks will be fatigued and the matrix material suffers high strain rates. Once the deforming ability of the PEKK-matrix is exceeded, these bridges fail causing catastrophic failure of the entire specimen. In correspondence to the the damage accumulation in fiber reinforced thermosets [9], this process can be depicted as be seen in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8: Damage accumulation in fiber reinforced high-performance thermoplastic materials

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The main purpose of this work was to investigate the influence of the degree of deformation on the fatigue properties of Discontinuous Aligned Fibers (DAF). In this sense, a number of concluding comments emerge:

- 1) Thermoforming of uni- and bidirectional DAF-composites occurs uniformly over the specimens until a state of deformation of approximately 2.5%. Further elongation, above 2.5% may lead to local deformation zones.
- 2) The deformation of DAF-material up to 9% increases its fatigue life-time.
- 3) The occurring fiber alignment during thermoforming up to deformation states of 3% and residual compressive stresses improve material properties.
- 4) Damage accumulation could not be monitored with ultrasonics and thermography; the specimens broke spontaneously. Progressive damaging of the DAF-specimen under dynamic load occurs on a microscopic level not accessible in detail for common nondestructive testing methods.

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